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Analysis of the Relation Between the Direct Taxes/Indirect Taxes Ratio and Inequality (Gini Coefficient) in Some European Union'S Member States (EU 27)

Florina Popa

Scientific Researcher III, PhD., Romanian Academy, Institute of National Economy, Bucharest, Romania, <https://orcid.org/0009-0006-9079-4933>

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Abstract: Objective of the study: The paper follows some theoretical aspects related to financial inclusion, through the perspective of some authors with concerns in the field, elements of the impact of financial inclusion on income inequality. At the same time, the paper carries out an analysis of the relation between the direct taxes/indirect taxes ratio and inequality (Gini coefficient), taking into account the changes that occurred in direct taxes and indirect taxes in some European Union'S Member States, between 2014-2022.

The methodology used in the paper was: studying the scientific literature in the field, selecting, synthesizing and interpreting the ideas retained through the own view of the author; Collecting data from the European Commission, DG Taxation and Customs Union, based on Eurostat, and Eurostat; processing data collected and drawing up the table necessary for the analyze of the correlation of indicators; analysis of indicators and the correlation between them, for European Union (EU 27),

each Member Country of the European Union (EU 27), for each year of the period 2014-2022, and drawing conclusions regarding the final results of the paper.

The results derived from the paper highlights some introductive aspects from theoretical literature in the the financial inclusion and an analysis of the evolution of changes in taxation, expressed by *the ratio between direct taxes and, respectively, indirect taxes*, for the period 2014-2022, for European Member Countries - EU 27.

The significance of the results is knowledge of the relation between taxation (direct tax/indirect tax ratio) and inequality, taking into account the changes appeared in direct and indirect taxes in some European Union Member States, in the interval of the years 2014 - 2022 (EU27).

Keywords: ratio between direct taxes and, respectively, indirect taxes; Gini coefficient (inequality); impact; European Union's (EU 27) Member States, financial inclusion.

Jel Classification: O11.

Some introductive elements on the financial inclusion

Financial inclusion provides individuals and businesses with access to financial products and services to meet some needs such as transactions, payments, savings, credit and insurance (World Bank Group, 2022).

Financial inclusion means efforts to increase individuals' access to financial products and services, to increase the quality of living standards, by removing barriers that exclude certain categories of the population from using these services (Grant, 2024)

Financial inclusion is referred to affordability to financial products and services, of people facing with financial problems (low income), poverty, marginalisation. In the last period, financial inclusion was seen as an instrument in achieving inclusive economic growth, macroeconomic stability, income inequality and poverty diminishing. (Chibba 2009, World Bank, 2014, qutoed in Omar, Inaba, 2020)

Increasing revenue from tax collection is a concern of political decision makers. Tax collection is a difficult task for all countries at different stages of development. An increase in the financial inclusion of individuals leads to an increase in income and ultimately, the increase in financial resources to the state budget, from taxes and fees. (Oz - Yalaman Gamze, 2019)

Financial inclusion indicators can be used to help setting its objectives at national level and to track the level of their achievement. In the context of some indicators of performance and survey mechanisms, favourable conditions are ensured for (World Bank Group, 2015):

- assessment of the state of financial inclusion;
- setting objectives;
- the identification of limits;
- the design of policies;
- monitoring and assessing the impact of policies.

When measuring financial inclusion, some indicators are considered, such as (World Bank Group, 2015):

- ✓ Access indicators reflect the extent of the penetration of financial services, such as the expansion of bank branches or point of sale (POS) in rural areas.
- ✓ Indicators of use assess how customers use financial services.
- ✓ Quality measures show the degree to which financial products and services meet the needs of customers, their area and the level of customer awareness towards the financial products.

Data published by Global Findex¹ helps to test the link between financial inclusion and tax revenue. To analyse the relationship between financial inclusion and tax revenues, with the help of Global Findex, the study done by Maherali, 2017 (quoted in Oz-Yalaman Gamze, 2019) uses various global data sets and develops a methodology to forecast the individual tax revenues that governments obtain until the year 2020, due to financial inclusion. (Oz-Yalaman Gamze, 2019). The authors note a positive relationship between the financial inclusion and tax revenues, in the analysis carried out, using the Global Findex data sets, having as tax bases, income from corporate tax, income from personal income tax and income from direct taxes and using the methodology of the data panel (Oz-Yalaman Gamze, 2019).

There are studies concerning the capacity of financial inclusion to decrease income inequality and, as a consequence, reduce poverty. Also there are researches on the impact of financial inclusion on economic growth, financial stability and income inequality (World Bank, 2014, qutoed in Omar, Inaba, 2020). García-Herrero and Turégano (2015), (qutoed in Omar, Inaba, 2020), in their research on the link between financial inclusion inconme inequality, observed the impact of financial inclusion on decreasing income inequality, with factors that economic developemnt and fiscal policy, as variables in regression. Salazar-Cantú et al. (2015) (qutoed in Omar, Inaba, 2020) observed the potential of financial inclusion to diminsh the income inequality, when it has a presence in progress, in Mexico. (Omar, Inaba, 2020).

Analysis of the relation between the direct taxes/indirect taxes ratio and inequality (Gini coefficient), in some European Union's Member States (EU 27), between 2014-2022

The possibility of knowing the correlation between taxes and inequality (Gini Coefficient) can be found by analyzing the impact of the elements of the tax structure on inequality (Gini coefficient). In this regard, the analysis aim at knowing the relation between taxation (the direct taxes/indirect

¹ Maherali A. (2017), p.1, quote Asli Demirguc-Kunt, Leora Klapper, Dorothe Singer, Peter Van Oudheusden (2014),, The Global Findex Database 2014 Measuring Financial Inclusion Around the World (The World Bank Group, n.d.), 2, <http://www.worldbank.org/en/programs/globalfindex>. and Maherali A. (2017), p.15, quote Demirguc-Kunt, Asli, Leora Klapper, Dorothe Singer, and Peter Van Oudheusden. "The Global Findex Database 2014 Measuring Financial Inclusion Around the World." The World Bank Group, n.d. <http://www.worldbank.org/en/programs/globalfindex>.

taxes ratio) and inequality (Gini coefficient), taking into account the changes that occurred in direct taxes and indirect taxes in some European Union's Member States (EU 27), between 2014-2022.

Direct taxes/indirect taxes ratio

2015-2014

Among the EU 27 countries, Denmark (-0.1), Luxembourg (0.2) and the Netherlands (0.1) registered changes in the tax structure (Direct Taxes/Indirect Taxes ratio) compared to the previous year, with different percentage values.

2016-2015

Changes in the fiscal structure (Direct Taxes/Indirect Taxes ratio) were recorded compared to the previous year in Belgium, Denmark, Austria, Portugal, negative percentage values (- 0.1 p.p.), and Germany and Romania positive values (0.1 p.p.).

2017-2016

The only countries where changes in the fiscal structure were recorded compared to the previous year were Belgium and the Netherlands (0.1p.p.), where the Direct Taxes/Indirect Taxes ratio increased.

2018-2017

Increases in the Direct Taxes/Indirect Taxes ratio, compared to the previous year were recorded in Ireland, Luxembourg, Austria - (0.1) and decreases were recorded in Denmark, Latvia, Romania and Finland (-1).

2019-2018

Increases in the Direct Tax/Indirect Tax ratio registered in Denmark (+0.2), Lithuania (+0.3), Malta (+0.1). The decrease occurred in Belgium (-0.1).

2020-2019

Countries such as: Estonia, Spain, Italy, Cyprus, Malta, Slovenia, (0.1) and Ireland (0.2) recorded increases in the Direct Taxes/Indirect Taxes ratio.

2021-2020

Increases in changes in taxation occur in: Denmark, Malta, Austria, Slovenia and Finland - (0.1). Decreases occur in: Czech Republic, Italy, Luxembourg, Hungary - (-0.1).

2022-2021

Positive values of the change in the Direct Taxes/Indirect Taxes ratio were recorded in: Belgium, Croatia, Lithuania, Hungary, Netherlands, Portugal, Romania, Finland (0.1) and Ireland (0.2). Negative values appear in Denmark (-0.2) and Greece (-0.1).

The evolution of changes in taxation, expressed by *the ratio between direct and, respectively, indirect taxes*, for the period 2014-2022, showed that most countries recorded increases and

decreases from one year to another, but there were also years in which the ratio remained unchanged compared to previous years. Synthetic, country data is presented in the table below:

Table 1

Status of annual changes to EU 27 Member States

Countries	Number of changes Direct taxes/Indirect taxes ratio in the period 2014-2022		Number of years with data remaining constant
	Increases	Decreases	
Denmark	2	4	2
Belgium	2	2	4
Ireland	3	-	5
Luxemburg	2	1	5
Malta	3	-	5
Austria	2	1	5
Netherlands	3	-	5
Romania	2	1	5
Finland	2	1	5
Other countries: Italy, Hungary, Portugal, Lithuania, Slovenia, had two years, each, with changes and six years, with values remaining constant compared to the previous year. Czech Republic, Germany, Estonia, Greece, Spain, Croatia, Cyprus, Latvia, each, one year with changes and seven years, with values remaining constant. Bulgaria, France, Poland, Slovakia, Sweden, in the interval 2014-2022, there were no changes, the values of the indicators remained constant compared to the previous year.			

Source: Processing based on data from European Commission, DG Taxation and Customs Union, based on Eurostat data https://taxation-customs.ec.europa.eu/taxation/economic-analysis/data-taxation-trends_en; Eurostat: Gini coefficient of equivalised disposable income by age, https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ilc_di12/default/table?lang=en

Conclusions

Financial inclusion' means efforts to increase individuals' access to financial products and services, to increase the quality of living standards, by removing barriers that exclude certain categories of the population from using these services (Grant, 2024).

A concern of political decision-makers is to increase revenues from tax collection. There is a link between financial inclusion and tax revenues. An increase in the financial inclusion of individuals

leads to an increase in income and finally, the increase in financial resources to the state budget, from taxes and fees (Oz-Yalaman Gamze 2019).

Many researches pursued the capacity of financial inclusion to decrease income inequality and, as a consequence, reduce poverty. Also there are researches on the impact of financial inclusion on economic growth, financial stability and income inequality. (Omar, Inaba, 2020).

A better understanding of the correlation between taxes and inequality (Gini coefficient) can be obtained by analyzing the impact of elements in the tax structure on inequality. In this regard, the following was investigated: the relationship between taxation (direct tax/indirect tax ratio) and inequality, taking into account the changes appeared in direct and indirect taxes in some European Union Member States, in the interval of the years 2014 - 2022.

The evolution of changes in taxation, expressed by the ratio between direct taxes and, respectively, indirect taxes, for the period 2014-2022 showed that in most countries there were increases and decreases from one year to another, but there were also years in which the ratio remained unchanged compared to previous years.

Statistically, it resulted that in the analyzed period (2014-2022), some countries had, in years, six changes in increases and decreases in the ratio Direct Taxes/Indirect Taxes, others, four, three changes, but a larger number was identified, with only one or two changes, in the interval. There were also cases of countries that had no changes, the values of the indicators remaining constant compared to the previous year (Bulgaria, France, Poland, Slovakia, Sweden).

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